

Original Article

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Corresponding Author:

Dr. Saeed Ahmad Bashir,
Sheikh Zayed medical
college Rahim Yar Khan
chohansaeed979@gmail.co
m

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**PREVALENCE OF COELIAC DISEASE
AMONG THE PATIENTS PRESENTING IN
THE OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. RABIA JAMIL, RIPHAH INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY ISLAMABAD
2. DR. ZAINAB MAHMOOD, MAYO HOSPITAL LAHORE
3. DR. SAEED AHMAD BASHIR, SHEIKH ZAYED MEDICAL COLLEGE RAHIM YAR KHAN

ABSTRACT:

Coeliac disease or celiac disease is a long-term autoimmune disorder that primarily affects the small intestine. Classic symptoms include gastrointestinal problems such as chronic diarrhoea, abdominal distention, malabsorption, loss of appetite, and among children failure to grow normally. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, symptoms of pale, loose stools, weight loss were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 100 patients presenting in the outdoor department were included in this study i.e., 50 males (50%) and 50 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 3.23 ± 2.23 years. Out of these patients, five patients were suspected as a case of coeliac disease. Further workup was suggested after that.

Keyword: Coeliac Disease

INTRODUCTION:

Coeliac disease or celiac disease is a long-term autoimmune disorder that primarily affects the small intestine. Classic symptoms include gastrointestinal problems such as chronic diarrhoea, abdominal distention, malabsorption, loss of appetite, and among children failure to grow normally. This often begins between six months and two years of age. Non-classic symptoms are more common, especially in people older than two years. There may be mild or absent gastrointestinal symptoms, a wide number of symptoms involving any part of the body or no obvious symptoms. Coeliac disease was first described in childhood; however, it may develop at any age. It is associated with other autoimmune diseases, such as Type 1 diabetes mellitus and Hashimoto's thyroiditis, among others.

Coeliac disease is caused by a reaction to gluten, a group of various proteins found in wheat and in other grains such as barley and rye. Moderate quantities of oats, free of contamination with other gluten-containing grains, are usually tolerated. The occurrence of problems may depend on the variety of oat. It occurs in people who are genetically predisposed. Upon exposure to gluten, an abnormal immune response may lead to the production of several different autoantibodies that can affect a number of different organs. In the small bowel, this causes an inflammatory reaction and may produce shortening of the villi lining the small intestine (villous atrophy). This affects the absorption of nutrients, frequently leading to anaemia.

Diagnosis is typically made by a combination of blood antibody tests and intestinal biopsies, helped by specific genetic testing. Making the diagnosis is not always straightforward. Frequently, the autoantibodies in the blood are negative, and many people have only minor intestinal changes with normal villi. People may have severe symptoms and they may be investigated for years before a diagnosis is achieved. Increasingly, the diagnosis is being made in people without symptoms, as a result of screening. Evidence regarding the effects of screening, however, is not sufficient to determine its usefulness.

While the disease is caused by a permanent intolerance to gluten proteins, it is distinct from wheat allergy, which is much rare (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, symptoms of pale, loose stools, weight loss were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 100 patients presenting in the outdoor department were included in this study i.e., 50 males (50%) and 50 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 3.23 ± 2.23 years. Out of these patients, five patients were suspected as a case of coeliac disease. Further workup was suggested after that.

DISCUSSION:

The classic symptoms of untreated coeliac disease include pale, loose, or greasy stools (steatorrhoea), and weight loss or failure to gain weight. Other common symptoms may be subtle or primarily occur in organs other than the bowel itself. It is also possible to have coeliac disease without any of the classic symptoms at all. This has been shown to comprise at least 43% of presentations in children. Further, many adults with subtle disease may only present with fatigue or anaemia. Many undiagnosed individuals who consider themselves asymptomatic are in fact not, but rather have become accustomed to living in a state of chronically compromised health. Indeed, after starting a gluten-free diet and subsequent improvement becomes evident, such individuals are often able to retrospectively recall and recognise prior symptoms of their untreated disease which they had mistakenly ignored.

Diarrhoea that is characteristic of coeliac disease is chronic, sometimes pale, of large volume, and abnormally bad smelling. Abdominal pain, cramping, bloating with abdominal distension (thought to be due to fermentative production of bowel gas), and mouth ulcers may be present. As the bowel becomes more damaged, a degree of lactose intolerance may develop. Frequently, the symptoms are ascribed to irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), only later to be recognised as coeliac disease. In populations of people with symptoms of IBS, a diagnosis of coeliac disease can be made in about 3.3% of cases, or 4x more likely than in general. Screening them for coeliac disease is recommended by the National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE), the British Society of Gastroenterology and the American College of Gastroenterology, but is of unclear benefit in North America.

Coeliac disease leads to an increased risk of both adenocarcinoma and lymphoma of the small bowel (enteropathy-associated T-cell lymphoma (EATL) or other non-Hodgkin lymphomas). This risk is also higher in first-degree relatives such as siblings, parents and children. Whether or not a gluten-free diet brings this risk back to baseline is not clear. Long-standing and untreated disease may lead to other complications, such as ulcerative jejunitis (ulcer formation of the small bowel) and stricturing (narrowing as a result of scarring with obstruction of the bowel) (4-6).

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